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Dental Emergency during Orthodontic Treatment arising due to Road Traffic Accident: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Road traffic accidents often result in traumatic dental injuries. With ongoing orthodontic treatment, the injuries to the orodental structures always present differently. Management of these patients require immediate surgical approach. This case report describes the immediate surgical treatment of relieving of soft tissue entrapment from the orthodontic brackets and wires following trauma.

Keywords: soft tissue lacerations, Orthodontic treatment, Road Traffic Accident

Introduction

Traumatic dental injuries (TDI) are a serious public health problem especially when a patient is undergoing orthodontic treatment. About 10% of the patient seeking orthodontic corrections experience orodental injuries.¹ When hit on the mouth while wearing them, they may cause injury to the lips. Sometimes they may get cut or caught on the braces. Braces hold the teeth together so any any trauma will likely cause less damage to the teeth. However, the teeth may still get damaged, less likely to get knocked out completely from the socket. The best way is to preserve the injured teeth in the mouth with the help of the braces.

Case report

19 years old female patient was referred to Department of Dentistry from the Emergency Department of Adarsh Hospital, KIRC Campus, Kalol with history of road traffic accident resulting in multiple lacerations on hands, elbows, knees accompanied with multiple lacerations intra and extra orally. No history of bleeding from nose, vomiting or nausea. Patient was undergoing orthodontic treatment due to which dental metal braces were bonded to upper and lower teeth. Due to the trauma resulting from falling off the bike, three of these braces had completely intruded into upper lip, however the NiTi wire was continuous and not broken or deformed which lead to upper lip entrapment into the dental braces thus leading to immobility of upper lip, swelling of lip and lacerations of the lip buccal mucosa, difficulty in speech. Also, the bracket from left central incisor was debonded and was embedded into the lip mucosa.

Also present were lacerations from the braces on the buccal mucosa of the lower lip. Extra oral lacerations on the upper lip and chin are also seen.

Mobility with upper front teeth were seen. (Fig.1)

Treatment done

The NiTi wire was cut in between from upper right canine to upper left lateral incisor. After cutting the NiTi wire it was found that the whole assembly (bracket with NiTi wire and orthodontic rubber band) was embedded into the upper lip with lip entrapment. The debonded bracket was then removed by surgically relieving the lip buccal mucosa. The Niti wire was cut in between upper right and left central incisor and the lip mucosa was relived surgically from the brackets.² However, the brackets were still bonded onto the teeth, so they were left on them to act as temporary splint for upper front teeth to be evaluated by IOPA (XRAY). 5.0 Vicryl Sutures were placed on the lip mucosa. Patient was than referred for OPG and CBCT for further course of treatment.

Discussion and Conclusion

The braces are affixed directly to the teeth and patients are at increased risk of oral injuries if any accident or sports injury occur. Brackets and wires add an additional element to oral injuries. They can cut, lacerate or even get entrapped or intruded inside to oral structures and the components can themselves be damaged.³ Most common are cheeks, lips and tongue. Usually rinsing with cold water does the trick. However, more severe cases require emergency surgical assistance that can help in evaluation of the underlying dental injuries to be evaluated thoroughly.⁴

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Conflict of Interest:

Nil

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